

HyQ: A Free Software Tool to Explore Pressure Surges and Rotating Machinery Dynamics

Stefano Castagnoli – MSc Mechanical Engineer - Chartered Member Order of Engineers – Milan, Italy

info@hyqflow.it [Stefano Castagnoli | LinkedIn](#)

Abstract

HyQ is a free standalone software for simulating hydraulic transients in pressurized systems using the Method of Characteristics (MoC). It supports networks composed of reservoirs, pipes, valves, surge tanks, pumps, and reaction turbines, and can reproduce pressure waves, mass oscillations, and the dynamics of rotating machinery including inertia and, for turbines, governor action.

Validation is carried out through case studies covering fundamental phenomena and practical applications: pressure wave propagation in pipelines, surge tank oscillations, pump shutdown transients, and turbine load rejections. Results are compared with analytical predictions, literature benchmarks, and commercial software, showing acceptable agreement.

Keywords: waterhammer, transient flow, free software, hydropower

1 Introduction

1.1 Background and significance of hydraulic transients

Hydraulic transients in pressurized systems are unsteady flow phenomena that occur as a result of rapid changes in flow conditions, such as valve closures, pump failures, or turbine shutdowns. These events can generate significant pressure surges that may compromise the structural integrity of hydraulic networks if not properly analyzed and controlled.

In the field of hydropower engineering, transient analysis plays a critical role in the design and operation of conduits, surge tanks, turbines, and control valves. Accurate simulation of these phenomena is therefore essential for ensuring both the safety and the efficiency of hydraulic infrastructures.

1.2 Objectives of the paper

The aim of this paper is to present HyQ, a software tool dedicated to the simulation of hydraulic transients in pressurized incompressible flow systems. The software is particularly suited for hydropower applications, where complex networks of penstocks, valves, turbines, and surge devices should be analyzed under dynamic conditions.

This paper is not intended to serve as a user manual; rather, it focuses on the modeling approach, internal architecture, and possible applications of the software, with the goal of providing engineers, researchers, and educators with a reliable and flexible simulation environment.

1.3 Brief description of the software

HyQ is a standalone simulation tool based on the Method of Characteristics (MoC).

The software allows users to build and simulate generic hydraulic networks composed of elements such as reservoirs, pipes, valves, turbines, pumps, and surge tanks. Each element is editable through dedicated dialog windows, enabling precise configuration of physical and operational parameters.

HyQ has a graphical user interface that supports intuitive modeling and direct interaction with the system layout. The software is free to download and use, though it is not open-source. It is designed to offer a practical and technically rigorous solution for modeling transient events in complex hydraulic systems.

2 Method of Calculation

2.1 Governing equations of unsteady flow in pressurized conduits

The simulation of hydraulic transients in pressurized systems is based on the one-dimensional equations of unsteady flow, which describe the conservation of mass and momentum along a pipe. Under typical assumptions - incompressible flow with elastic pipe walls, negligible radial velocity components, the governing equations can be written as follows:

$$\frac{\partial Q}{\partial t} + gA \frac{\partial H}{\partial x} + \frac{f}{D} Q|Q| = 0$$
$$\frac{\partial H}{\partial t} + \frac{a^2}{gA} \frac{\partial Q}{\partial x} = 0$$

These equations form a system of hyperbolic partial differential equations (PDEs), where the unknowns are usually the piezometric head H and the discharge Q .

2.2 The Method of Characteristics

To solve the above system numerically, HyQ uses the MoC, a robust and well-established technique for dealing with hyperbolic PDEs. The MoC transforms the original system into two ordinary differential equations along specific directions in the space-time domain, known as characteristic lines.

These lines, indicated as C^+ and C^- , represent the directions along which pressure waves propagate upstream and downstream, respectively. Along each characteristic, the combined effects of inertia, pressure, and friction are integrated to yield relations that can be evaluated numerically.

Figure 1 - Computational Grid for MoC

The computational domain is discretized into a grid of space and time steps, where the intersection points correspond to locations where the solution is updated using known values from previous time steps.

2.3 Numerical solution scheme

The numerical solution is obtained by applying the characteristic relations along each grid point. This leads to two explicit formulas, each corresponding to one characteristic direction, that are used to compute the unknowns at the current time step based on values from the previous step.

$$C^+ \quad Q_P - Q_A + \frac{gA}{a}(H_P - H_A) + \frac{f\Delta t}{2DA}Q_A|Q_A| = 0$$

$$C^- \quad Q_P - Q_B - \frac{gA}{a}(H_P - H_B) + \frac{f\Delta t}{2DA}Q_B|Q_B| = 0$$

These expressions incorporate the effects of wave speed, pipe geometry, frictional losses, and boundary conditions. Special treatment is applied at junctions and boundaries to ensure continuity of flow and proper interaction with hydraulic elements such as valves, turbines, reservoirs, and pumps.

2.4 Stability condition

Being MoC an explicit scheme, its numerical stability is governed by the Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy (CFL) condition, which sets an upper bound on the time step

Δt relative to the spatial step Δx and the wave speed a : $\Delta t \leq \Delta x/a$

2.5 Effects of violating the stability condition

If the CFL condition is violated, the numerical solution is normally not achieved.

On the other hand, an excessively small Courant number (i.e., a much smaller time step than required) may introduce numerical diffusivity, smoothing pressure waves and attenuating sharp gradients. While stable, such a solution may underestimate peak pressures and distort the transient response.

To prevent these issues, HyQ automatically checks the CFL condition before starting the simulation. If the stability criterion is not satisfied (i.e., if $\frac{a\Delta t}{\Delta x} > 1$ in any pipe segment), the software will either block the execution and notify the user or, in marginal cases, issue a warning suggesting refinement of the spatial or temporal discretization.

3 Software Architecture and Models

3.1 Structure and handling of network topology

The definition of a hydraulic system in HyQ begins with the placement of hydraulic blocks representing physical components such as reservoirs, turbines, pumps, or valves. These blocks are then interconnected using pipe elements, which define the conduits through which flow propagates.

Each connection must be explicitly drawn from the outlet port of one element to the inlet port of another. This orientation determines the positive flow direction for the discharge variable Q . The connection logic is unidirectional by design, reflecting the physical assumption that the sign of the flow rate will be defined relative to the direction in which the pipe is traced.

Hydraulic blocks are equipped with one inlet port and one outlet port, each capable of accommodating a single connection. An exception to this rule is the manifold element, which is specifically designed to support branching configurations. Manifolds can accept multiple inlets or outlets and are used to represent junctions or distribution nodes in the network.

The properties of all blocks - including pipes - can be accessed and edited through dialog windows, which open with a double-click on the corresponding element. These dialogs allow the user to assign physical and operational parameters such as dimensions, initial conditions, boundary behavior, and control settings.

The next section provides a detailed overview of the available hydraulic elements, including their numerical models, capabilities, and current limitations.

3.2 Hydraulic elements and their representation

This section provides a detailed overview of the available hydraulic elements, including their numerical models, capabilities, and current limitations. All elements other than pipes are treated as boundary elements. The solution requires a computational approach that combines their defining equations with one of the two characteristic equations C^+ and C^- to close the system of equations at the pipe interface.

3.2.1 Piping

The modeling of pipes in HyQ is based on MoC, as described in the previous chapter. Pipes are assumed to have constant circular cross-sections, characterized by a diameter D . If a non-circular geometry is to be represented, the user must approximate it by specifying an equivalent diameter D^* and a corresponding friction coefficient, so as to match the same hydraulic resistance and inertance (typically expressed as L/gA).

Friction losses along the pipe are modeled using the Manning equation. Since HyQ employs a lumped parameter approach, the Manning coefficient n should also account for any localized head losses due to fittings, bends, transitions, or valves located along the pipe.

Each pipe must be discretized into N computational points, with the two end points coinciding with the upstream and downstream boundaries. The total length L of the pipe is divided into $N-1$ segments of equal size, with spatial step $\Delta x = L/(N-1)$. The value of N must be an odd number, a requirement imposed by the numerical structure of the MoC implementation.

A thorough discussion on the selection of an appropriate discretization density is beyond the scope of this paper and is referred to standard hydraulic transient literature, such as [2].

3.2.2 Reservoirs

Reservoirs in HyQ are modeled as ideal boundary elements with infinite storage capacity and constant water level. They act as fixed-head boundaries and are typically used to represent upstream basins or downstream tailraces in hydropower systems.

Each reservoir requires as input the elevation of the connection point - i.e., the altitude at which the pipe is connected to the reservoir's inlet or outlet port. This elevation is necessary to correctly compute the piezometric head at the interface with the hydraulic network.

3.2.3 Surge Tanks

HyQ supports the modeling of surge tanks with a constant cross-sectional area A_t , connected to the main pipeline through a throttling device located at elevation Z_o , with an effective opening area A_o .

Figure 2 - Scheme of Surge Tank Model

The throttling effect at the base of the surge tank is represented by a local head loss of the form:

$$\Delta H = \frac{K_{i/o} Q_p |Q_p|}{2g A_o^2}$$

where K is a loss coefficient that can be specified separately for inflow conditions ($Q_p > 0$, flow entering the surge tank) and outflow conditions ($Q_p < 0$, flow returning to the main conduit). This allows modelling an asymmetric behavior during oscillatory transients, which is common in surge tank dynamics.

The general surge tank behavior is governed by the following differential equation:

$$\frac{L_z}{gA_t} \frac{dQ_p}{dt} = H_p - Z_o - \Delta H$$

In HyQ, this equation is solved using a simplified model that neglects the inertial term, which accounts for vertical acceleration of the water column within the surge tank. The previous equation is therefore simplified:

$$H_p - Z_o - \Delta H = 0$$

This simplification is widely accepted in many hydropower applications, where the tank cross-section is relatively large and the internal accelerations have a minor influence on the overall transient response.

3.2.4 Valves

Valves in HyQ are modeled as flow control elements that introduce head losses dependent on their degree of opening. They have to be positioned between two pipes.

The head loss introduced by the valve is modeled using a loss coefficient K that depends on the valve opening y , which itself may be a function of time t , i.e., $K = K(y(t))$. The head loss formulation takes the form:

$$\Delta H = K(y) \frac{Q|Q|}{2gA^2}$$

Alternatively, the valve can be modeled in the discharge form:

$$Q = C(y)A\sqrt{2g\Delta H}$$

where A is the nominal cross-sectional area of the valve and $C(y)$ is the discharge coefficient as a function of the valve opening.

The user is required to specify:

- A reference diameter D for the valve, used to compute the nominal area A
- A valve opening law $y(t)$, defined as a table of points over time
- A modeling approach for the loss or discharge coefficient

HyQ includes three modeling approaches for computing $K(y)$ or $C(y)$:

(a) Power law: The user defines a value K_0 corresponding to the fully open condition, and the loss coefficient varies with the valve opening as:

$$K(y) = K_0/y^n$$

where n is an exponent defined by the user.

(b) Standard valve database: HyQ includes a small built-in database of four typical valve types, with characteristic discharge curves derived from technical literature [3].

(c) Custom polynomial definition: The user defines the discharge coefficient $C(y)$ via a fifth-order polynomial:

$$C(y) = a_0 + a_1y + a_2y^2 + \dots + a_5y^5$$

It is generally recommended to set $a_0 = 0$ to ensure that the flow rate is zero when the valve is closed. The definition of the polynomial coefficients is entirely left to the user, and no curve-fitting or identification tools are included in HyQ.

3.2.5 Turbines

HyQ includes a dedicated model for reaction turbines, designed to simulate their dynamic behavior during hydraulic transients. The model focuses on situations typical of hydropower systems, such as load rejection, load acceptance, and regulation transients.

From a computational point of view, the turbine is treated as a boundary element that couples the hydraulic system with a rotating mass. The model includes the rotational inertia of the turbine-generator shaft.

Hydromechanical Model

The turbine model is based on dimensionless characteristic curves, expressed in terms of unit discharge and unit torque:

$$Q_{11} = f_Q(N_{11}, y) \quad T_{11} = f_T(N_{11}, y)$$

Where:

$$N_{11} = N_R D / \sqrt{H_t}$$

$$Q_{11} = Q / (D^2 \sqrt{H_R})$$

$$T_{11} = T / (D^3 H_R)$$

Figure 3 - Examples of Turbine Models in HyQ

HyQ provides three ways to define turbine behavior:

- A built-in library with a set of typical reaction turbine characteristics.
- The option to import user-defined characteristic curves.
- calculation of the turbine discharge according to the model described by Torbjørn K. Nielsen in [6]

$$gH = gH_R \left(\frac{Q}{yQ_R} \right)^2 + s(\omega^2 - \omega_R^2)$$

where s represents a turbine throttling coefficient and is determined from the inlet and outlet runner diameters D_1 and D_2 :

$$s = \frac{D_1^2}{8} \left(1 - \frac{D_2^2}{D_1^2} \right)$$

The transient behavior of the turbine is also governed by the rotational dynamics of the coupled rotating masses, which are modeled through the integration of the equation of motion.

$$J_T \frac{d\omega}{dt} = T - T_{El}$$

Speed Governor

The speed governor model implemented in HyQ simulates the action of a mechanical speed governor (as described in [4]) that adjusts the gate opening $y(t)$ based on the deviation from nominal speed. This enables simulation of regulation phenomena such as:

- Partial load rejection: the speed governor attempts to maintain system stability.
- Load acceptance: the governor increases gate opening to meet the load demand.

The dynamics of the wicket gates are user-defined and are taken into account during the simulation, except in the case of a regulation transient, where the gate movement is instead governed by the speed governor.

Figure 4 - HYQ Model of Speed Governor (from USACE)

3.2.6 Pumps

HyQ allows for the simulation of transient events involving pumps, such as startup and shutdown sequences. These models are particularly suited for general-purpose pumping systems rather than for hydropower installations. The pump operates at constant full opening (i.e., no regulation), and the model can simulate unsteady behavior resulting from hydraulic and mechanical interactions during transients.

Mathematical Model

The transient behavior of pumps in HyQ is modeled using the Suter curves, which provides a generalized way to represent pump performance under both normal and reverse flow conditions. The model relies on dimensionless variables, defined as follows, where the subscript R denotes the rated values.

$$v = Q/Q_R \quad h = H/H_R \quad \alpha = N/N_R \quad \beta = T/T_R$$

To express the machine characteristics over the four quadrants, the following functions are introduced:

$$W_H(\theta) = \frac{h}{\alpha^2 + v^2}$$

$$W_B(\theta) = \frac{\beta}{\alpha^2 + v^2}$$

$$\theta = \pi + \text{atan}\left(\frac{v}{\alpha}\right)$$

Figure 5 – Pump Model in the Four Quadrants

With the formulation described above, the equation governing the rotational dynamics of the pump shaft can be expressed as:

$$J_P \frac{2\pi N_R}{60} \frac{d\alpha}{dt} = T_R W_B (\alpha^2 + v^2)$$

4 Validation and Case Studies

This chapter presents a set of validation exercises and case studies aimed at verifying the accuracy of HyQ simulation engine. The tests will cover both fundamental hydraulic phenomena and practical operational scenarios involving pumps and turbines.

- **Numerical Validation:** Assessing HyQ's ability to reproduce well-known theoretical results, such as pressure wave propagation and mass oscillation dynamics.
- **Applied Case Studies:** Demonstrating HyQ's performance in realistic transients involving pump and turbine units, including start-up, shutdown, and load rejection events.

Each case is selected to isolate specific modeling features and to highlight the key physical mechanisms captured by the software. When possible, results are compared with analytical solutions, or reference literature.

The aim is not only to prove that the numerical models work correctly, but also to show how they can be applied to real-world situations.

4.1 Pressure Wave Propagation – Valve Closure Test

This test is designed to validate HyQ's ability to accurately capture pressure wave propagation in a pipeline following a rapid valve closure. The case reproduces a classical water hammer scenario, where the pressure rise and wave reflection at boundaries can be predicted analytically.

Figure 6 - HyQ model for Valve Closure Test

The levels in the upstream and downstream tanks are 150.00 m.asl and 0.00 m.asl, respectively. The valve has a loss coefficient $K_o = 496$ and closes in 0.1 s. A time integration step of $\Delta t = 0.0083$ s was selected, corresponding to $\Delta x/a$.

The selection of the time step Δt is critical to ensure numerical accuracy, correctly capture the wave propagation and to avoid artificial numerical diffusion. Pipe characteristics are shown in table 1.

Table 1

Conduits					
N°	Q [m³/s]	D [m]	L [m]	a [m/s]	σ_{manning}
1	0.468	0.5	600	1200	0.018
2	0.468	1.0	20	1200	0.000

A simple calculation shows that, based on this model, a maximum pressure rise at the valve equal to $\Delta H = aQ/gA = 291$ m is expected, while the period of the oscillation should be $T = 4L/a = 2$ s.

The following graph, obtained from the HyQ simulation, shows the trend of H upstream of the valve and confirms the expected results.

Figure 7 - Head Surge Effect Upstream of Valve - Sudden Closure

4.2 Validation of Mass Oscillation Phenomena

This test case focuses on the validation of HyQ's ability to simulate mass oscillation transients, in surge tanks.

The system under investigation consists of an upstream and a downstream reservoir with a static head difference of 700 meters. Between them lies a pressurized tunnel–surge tank–penstock configuration, with a throttling valve (loss coefficient $K = 368$) installed at the

downstream end to trigger the transient event. The valve closure is modeled using a nonlinear law defined as:

$$y(t) = 1 - (t/T_c)^{0.75} \quad \text{with } T_c = 2.1 \text{ s}$$

Although a valve is also present at the head of the penstock, it remains fully open throughout the simulation and does not affect the transient.

Figure 8 - HyQ Model to Compute Mass Oscillation in a Surge Tank

This case study has already been presented in [5] while presenting the simulation software SIMSEN, and is revisited here to assess HyQ performance.

The surge tank has a constant cross-sectional area of 38.48 m² and is not equipped with any throttling device at its base. The pipe layout and physical properties of the system are detailed in table 2.

Table 2

Conduits					
N°	Q [m³/s]	D [m]	L [m]	a [m/s]	σ_{manning}
1	30.4	3.57	5000	1100	0.0049
2	30.4	2.52	22	1100	0.0046
3	30.4	2.52	1100	1100	0.0046
4	30.4	4.00	22	1100	0.0046

The results of the HyQ simulation shown in Fig. 9 are consistent with those presented in [5] and with the analytical formulations [3] used to estimate water level rise and the period of mass oscillations in a frictionless system. Assuming here that L is the length of the power tunnel, A_p its cross-sectional area, and A_t the cross-sectional area of the surge tank:

$$\Delta Z = Q \sqrt{\frac{L}{gA_p A_t}} \quad \frac{T}{2} = \pi \sqrt{\frac{L A_t}{g A_p}}$$

4.3 Full Load Rejection of a Reaction Turbine

This case study focuses on validating the response of HyQ in simulating a full load rejection of a reaction turbine without the intervention of the speed governor. The aim is to evaluate the accuracy of the transient hydraulic and mechanical response, particularly the pressure surges and rotor overspeed, by comparing the

results to a benchmark problem presented in literature [2].

Figure 9 - Water Level (upper graph) and In/out Flow in the Surge Tank (lower graph)

In this scenario, the unit is initially generating 61.7 MW when, following a load rejection, the wicket gates begin closing from 60% opening and reach full closure in 4.2 s. The gross head across the turbine, defined as the elevation difference between the upstream reservoir and the tailrace, is 80 m.

Figure 10 - HyQ Model to Compute Turbine Transient

The turbine is modeled using the characteristic curves corresponding to a specific speed of $N_q = 78$ selected from the internal HyQ database. The hydraulic system layout and the turbine parameters are reported in the following table.

Table 3

Conduits					
N°	Q	D	L	A	α_{manning}
	[m ³ /s]	[m]	[m]	[m ²]	
1	86.8	5.48	125	1250	0.045
2	86.8	8.00	12.5	1250	0.010

Turbine & Generator					
H _R	Q _R	N _R	T _R	J _T	N _q
[m]	[m ³ /s]	[rpm]	[Nm]	[kgm ²]	[metric]
82	114.0	200	4115825	1496000	78.3

The results of the simulation are compared below in Fig. 11 with those reported in the reference literature, showing an overall acceptable agreement. Minor discrepancies are to be expected, as not all boundary conditions are fully specified in the original source (e.g., the exact characteristic curves used, precise closure timings, etc.).

Figure 11 - Turbine Transient - Comparison between HyQ and Literature Results

4.4 Validation Case Study: Pump Transient Simulation

This final case study focuses on the validation of HyQ's pump transient simulation. The modeled system consists of a simple pump installation with an inlet pipe (suction side) and an outlet pipe (discharge side), without any intermediate valves or surge protection devices. A sudden pump shutdown is simulated, and the resulting transient behavior is compared with results from the commercial software AFT_Impulse8-(Demo), using the available model *pump_trip.imp*. At the moment of the

pump shutdown, the geodetic head difference between the upstream and downstream reservoirs is 58 m

Figure 12 - HyQ model of Pumping System

The system layout and hydraulic parameters are summarized in the following table. The pump model used in HyQ is selected from its internal database. Due to database limitations, the curve corresponding to a specific speed of $N_s = 15.7$ is used, although the rated pump values would suggest a lower specific speed around $N_s = 8.9$.

Table 4

Conduits					
N°	Q	D	L	a	n_{Manning}
	[m ³ /s]	[m]	[m]	[m/s]	
1	0.0315	0.1022	20	1000	0.009
2	0.0315	0.1022	300	1000	0.009

Pump - Motor

H _R	Q _R	N _R	T _R	J _R	N _s
[m]	[m ³ /s]	[rpm]	[Nm]	[kgm ²]	[metric]
116	0.0319	1760	247	1.05	15.7

The comparison of the transient results for flow rate, rotational speed, and pump head shows a reasonably good agreement between HyQ and AFT Impulse. In the figure, the HyQ results are displayed on the right-hand side, while the AFT Impulse results are shown on the left.

Figure 13 - Transient in Pumping System. Comparison between AFT Impulse and HyQ

5 Software Overview and Graphical Interface

At the end of the paper, a brief overview of HyQ's graphical user interface is presented to illustrate its usability. On the left side of the User Interface, the main panel is dedicated to the visual representation of the hydraulic model. Elements are added by selecting them from a contextual menu, accessible via right-click. The top menu bar provides options to save and reopen models, as well as to launch the steady-state calculation (pre-simulation or stabilization) and transient simulation procedures. Simulation results can also be exported to Excel for further analysis.

Figure 14 - HyQ Graphic Interface

On the right side of the interface, three main panels are available: a) transient control, including timing, integration step, and fluid properties; b) graphical display of simulation results; and c) a console showing messages about the progress of the simulation.

6 Conclusions

The validation exercises confirm that HyQ is capable of reproducing the main physical phenomena of hydraulic transients, including pressure wave propagation, mass oscillations, and the dynamic response of rotating machinery. Comparisons with analytical formulations, literature benchmarks, and commercial software show acceptable agreement, demonstrating that HyQ provides reliable results for engineering and educational applications.

Several areas for future development remain. The current surge tank model does not account for water column inertia and cannot represent variable cross-section tanks, which limits its applicability in some complex layouts. For rotating machinery, the software currently handles only single transient events, without the possibility of simulating sequences such as a full load rejection followed by a rapid restart. In addition, turbine speed governor models could be enhanced to support more generic transfer functions, extending their applicability beyond a single type of governor.

HyQ is freely available for download at www.hyqflow.it.

7 Notations

A	wave celerity
α	non dimensional speed in pump Suter curves
A	general cross section
A_t	surge tank cross section
A_t	power tunnel cross section
A_o	surge tank throttle section
β	non dimensional torque in pump Suter curves
C	valve flow coefficient
C⁺	left and right characteristic
D	pipe or runner diameter
F	Darcy friction coefficient
G	gravity acceleration 9.81 m/s ²
h	non dimensional head in pump Suter curves
H	total head
H_p	total head at surge tank throttle
H_R	rated net head – pump turbine
ΔH	head loss
J_v, J_p	rot. inertia (turbine + generator / pump+motor)
K	general head loss coefficient
K_{in out}	head loss coeff at surge tank throttle
K_o	head loss coeff with valve fully open
L	pipe length
L_z	surge tank oscillation above throttle elevation
n	Manning friction coefficient
v	non dimensional discharge in pump Suter curves
N	rotating speed (rpm) o number of pipe sections (MoC)
N_q	specific speed turbine $N_q = NQ^{0.5}/H^{0.75}$
N_R	rated speed of rotating machine
N_s	specific speed pump $N_s = NQ^{0.5}/H^{0.75}$
N₁₁	turbine unit-speed
Q	volumetric discharge
Q_P	volumetric discharge through surge tank throttle
Q_R	rated discharge pump or turbine
Q₁₁	turbine unit-discharge
t	time
Δt	time-step in integrating equations
T	torque (hydraulic) or oscillation period
T_C	valve closing time
T_{EL}	torque (electric)
T_R	rated torque in rotating machines
T₁₁	turbine unit-torque
Θ	quadrant-related variable in pump Suter model
X	curvilinear abscissa
Δx	Spatial integration step in MoC
Y	valve or turbine distributor opening (decimal)
Z	water level in surge tank
Z_o	elevation of surge tank throttle
ω	rotating speed of turbines and pumps – rad/s

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